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IMPROVEMENT OF CONVECTIVE DRYING TECHNOLOGY FOR ONION IN CUBIC FORM** Rakhmatov Gulomjon Rakhmonberdiyevich****Fergana State University*

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*Received: 19 May 2026 | Accepted: 19 May 2026***ABSTRACT**

This study analyzes the convective drying technology of onion, which is highly relevant for the canning industry. Onion raw material was cut into cubes with thicknesses of 4.0 mm, 6.0 mm, and 8.0 mm, and the duration and efficiency of drying were determined experimentally. The results showed that reducing the cutting thickness significantly shortens the drying time and ensures more uniform drying of the product. The kinetics of drying, equilibrium moisture content, and factors affecting product quality were examined in detail. The obtained data contribute to the improvement of energy-efficient and high-quality onion drying technology for small enterprises.

Keywords: onion, convective drying, cutting thickness, drying kinetics, artificial drying technology, cubic shape, equilibrium moisture content.

Introduction.

The canning industry in the Republic of Uzbekistan is developing rapidly under market economy conditions. The establishment of new enterprises and the expansion of product range are increasing the demand for processing fruits and vegetables. Fruits and vegetables serve as important sources of easily digestible carbohydrates, organic acids, vitamins, and biologically active compounds essential for the human body. However, due to the difficulty of long-term storage and transportation of fresh produce, artificial drying technologies hold significant importance.

Literature Review

In industry, convective, radiation, and conductive drying methods are commonly used. In convective drying, heat is transferred through a gas (air), which also facilitates moisture removal. The kinetics of the drying process depend on internal and external heat and mass transfer, as well as the forms of moisture bonding with the material (chemical, colloidal, osmotic, and capillary). Equilibrium moisture content represents the state of equilibrium between the product and the drying agent and depends on temperature and relative air humidity. Removing moisture to the equilibrium level is crucial for preserving product quality and saving energy.

Methodology

Literature indicates that the correct selection of drying regime depends on the morphological properties of the product, the degree of cutting, and pre-treatment methods. Convective drying is considered one

of the most effective methods for onions, cabbage, carrots, and other vegetables (Bo'riev et al., 1996; Xudayberdiyev and Mamatov, 2019). The aim of this study is to improve the convective drying technology of onion in cubic form with different thicknesses and to substantiate energy-efficient regimes for small enterprises.

Figure 1. Convective drying apparatus.

Results.

In the research, onion raw material grown in Uzbekistan was used. The preparation stages for drying included sorting, washing, peeling, and cutting into cubes. Cutting was performed using knives moving in frontal, horizontal, and profile planes. Due to the layered structure of onion, it naturally separates during cutting; therefore, the main parameter was the cutting thickness (4.0 mm, 6.0 mm, and 8.0 mm). Drying was carried out in an artificial convective drying apparatus (Figure 1). Three replications were performed for each variant. The drying time was recorded separately for each thickness. Uniform drying of the product and the dynamics of moisture removal were monitored during the process.

Table 1.

Chemical composition of dried vegetables
(according to E.N. Volkov)

Product	Composition Dry matter (%)	Protein (%)	Carbohydrates (%)	Calories Kcal/100 g.
Carrot	85.0	8.47	52.96	247.6
Cabbage	86.0	11.41	39.61	214.2
Onion	84.0	12.74	52.96	265.7

Drying at 4.0 mm thickness took an average of 40 minutes, at 6.0 mm - 45 minutes, and at 8.0 mm - 52 minutes. Thus, reducing the cutting thickness to 4.0 mm shortened the drying time by 23% compared to 8.0 mm. In all variants, the product dried uniformly without deformation.

Table 2.

Effect of onion cutting thickness on drying time

Cutting thickness, mm	Replications	Drying time, min.
4.0	1	35.0
	2	40.0
	3	45.0
	Average	40.0
6.0	1	42.0
	2	45.0
	3	48.0
	Average	45.0
8.0	1	50.5
	2	52.0
	3	54.0
	Average	52.0

The experimental results confirm that cutting thickness is a key parameter in convective drying of onion. As thickness decreases, external and internal moisture diffusion accelerates, improving drying kinetics. This phenomenon is explained by the rapid removal of moisture from the product surface and cell structure (figure 2).

Figure 2. Drying time for individual replications at different cutting thicknesses

In the initial stage of drying, the rate is high and then stabilizes. Under optimal regimes, the balance between external and internal diffusion is maintained, which helps preserve product quality (color, taste, and nutrients). The 4.0 mm cubic shape is the most optimal variant, as it reduces energy consumption and prevents product losses.

Discussion

Cubic, strip, or ring-shaped dried onions allow uniform distribution in automatic packaging lines and good mixing in ready-to-eat meals. The degree of crumbling should not exceed 5–8%; otherwise, drying conditions become more difficult and standard yield decreases.

The results enable more efficient use of existing convective dryers in small enterprises and increase energy efficiency.

Conclusion

It was determined that convective drying of onion in 4.0 mm thick cubic form is the most effective and energy-efficient option. The drying time was reduced to 40 minutes, the product dried uniformly, and its quality was maintained

at a high level. The obtained results provide opportunities to improve the onion drying process in the canning industry of Uzbekistan and offer practical recommendations for small enterprises.

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